

Table 1. Incidence of GLH at RRS, Tirur, India. Jul-Sep 1992.^a

Week	Incidence	
	Light trap (no.)	Field (no./25 sweeps)
3 Jul	436	10
10 Jul	1157	30
17 Jul	535	40
24 Jul	1794	110*
31 Jul	1354	330*
7 Aug	7064	920*
14 Aug	86234	150*
21 Aug	13091	40
28 Aug	1192	45
4 Sep	739	15

^a* = above economic threshold level of 60 GLH/25 sweeps.

(*Nephotettix virescens*), was prevalent from Jul to Aug 1992 (Table 1).

Eighty rice entries (69 cultures) and 11 varieties from the 1992 International Irrigated Rice Yield Nursery (early), Advanced Yield Trial (mid-early), and Multilocation Trial III along with susceptible check TN1 were planted in 5-m² plots during the second week of Jul 1992. Plants were infected with RTD at tillering, stem elongation, and booting stages. Reactions varied. Each entry was scored for RTD 45 d after transplanting using the methodology from the 1991 International Rice Tungro Nursery.

The entries and check were screened for their reaction to GLH under screenhouse conditions using the seedbox test. Seedlings were infested with five 2d- and 3d-instar GLH nymphs 7 d after seeding. Entries were scored using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* when 90% of TN1 plants were dead.

None of the entries were resistant to RTD. Twenty-five were moderately resistant (Table 2), 27 moderately susceptible, 19 susceptible, and 9 highly susceptible. ■

Table 2. Rice cultures moderately resistant to RTD. RRS, Tirur, India.

Entry	Parentage	GLH score ^a	RTD (%)	RTD score ^b
IET12888	BR51/KAU2335-2	1	1.7	2
IET12461	IR36/KJT35-3	1	2.2	2
IET12419	IR36/Jothi	1	2.6	2
IR59606-119-3	IR44592-62/IR20289-94	1	2.7	2
IET12488	Ratna/IR36	3	3.2	2
IET12928	IR50/P338	3	4.3	2
IET12867	Palman 579/IR54	3	4.4	2
IET12355	IR50/IR36	3	5.1	3
TNRH6	IR628294/Pusa/50R	3	5.9	3
IET12914	IR50/P33/IR50/Ratna	3	6.3	3
IET12351	IR50/IET7918	3	6.5	3
TNRH1	IR628294/IR10198-66-2 R	3	7.1	3
IR56382-17-3-2	IR28239-94/IR24632-34	5	7.5	3
IR58099-41-2-3	IR35366-90/IR324-29-47	5	7.5	3
IR57301-195-3-3	IR35293-125/IR32429-47	5	7.5	3
IR50	IR2153/IR28//IR36	5	7.6	3
RP1451-92-21-9	Rasi/Finegora	5	8.2	3
IET12428	IET5233/IR2153-26	5	8.8	3
BG850-2	BG380/BG367-4	5	8.9	3
IET12929	KAU8759	5	9.0	3
IR57311-95-2-3	IR39268-57/IR32429//IR42005-47	5	9.1	3
IET12891	Ratna/IR36	5	9.6	3
IET12402	Govind/Ranikajar	5	9.7	3
IR29725-117-2-3-3	IR19661-131/IR9125-209	5	9.8	3
IR53292-159-1-2-3	IR4563-52/IR31802-48	5	10.0	3
TN1 (susceptible check)	-	9	95.0	9

^aScored using 1-9 scale in SES. ^bScored using the methodology from the 1991 International Rice Tungro Nursery.

Pest resistance—insects

Resistance to whitebacked planthopper in wild and cultivated rices

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We evaluated wild rice species *Oryza officinalis*, *O. punctata*, and *O. latifolia* and genetically diverse rice varieties N22 (Wbph 1), ARC10239 (Wbph 1), Ptb33 (Wbph 3), Podwi A8 (Wbph 4), N'diang Marie (Wbph 5), IR2035-117-3 (Wbph 1 + Wbph 2), and Chaia Anaser (Wbph 1 + Wbph 3) for resistance to the white-

Damage ratings of selected wild and cultivated rices after infestation by WBPH nymphs in free-choice test.^a TNAU, Coimbatore, India.

Species/variety	IRRI accession number	Damage rating (d after infestation)		
		7	11	15
<i>O. officinalis</i>	101114	1.0 c	1.0 e	1.0 d
<i>O. punctata</i>	101439	1.0 c	1.0 e	1.4 d
<i>O. latifolia</i>	100963	1.0 c	1.0 e	1.0 d
<i>O. sativa</i>				
N22	4819	1.0 c	5.4 b	9.0 a
ARC10239	20803	1.0 c	3.4 c	9.0 a
Ptb33	19325	1.0 c	2.2 d	7.0 c
Podwi A8	15201	2.6 b	6.2 b	9.0 a
N'diang Marie	15859	1.0 c	3.4 c	8.2 b
IR2035-117-3	-	1.0 c	2.6 cde	7.4 bc
Chaia Anaser	16197	1.0 c	3.0 cd	7.8 bc
TN1		8.6 a	9.0 a	9.0 a

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. Av of 5 replications.

backed planthopper (WBPH) *Sogatella furcifera* (Horvath) using the seedbox screening technique.

Seeds were sown in 40-cm rows, about 2-3 cm apart, in wooden trays (60 × 45 × 10 cm) in a greenhouse. TN1 was the susceptible check. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design, with five replications of

each wild species and variety. Seven days after sowing, seedlings were thinned to 15 per row and infested with 6-8 2d-instar WBPH nymphs per seedling. Plant damage was scored on a 0-9 scale at 7, 11, and 15 d after infestation (DAI).

The test entries exhibited resistance at 7 DAI. Mean damage ranged from 1 to 2.6, with TN1 rating 8.6 (see table). At

11 DAI, the wild rices rated 1, the cultivated varieties ranged from 2.2 to 6.2, and TN1, 9. At 15 DAI, the wild rices had maintained their extremely high level of resistance; the varieties exhibited moderately susceptible to susceptible reactions (see table). ■

Integrated germplasm improvement—irrigated

Xiang-zhong Xian No. 3: a high-yielding, widely useful rice variety in Hunan, China

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Xiang-zhong Xian No. 3 is derived from the cross Xiang-zhao Xian No. 1///Ai-Bao//IR36/Shuang-Gui 36. It is a high-yielding, widely useful indica variety with multiple resistance. It was released in Jan 1992.

Xiang-zhong Xian No. 3 is resistant to whitebacked planthopper, brown planthopper, rice blast, and lodging. It responds well to high fertilizer levels.

Xiang-zhong Xian No. 3 performed well in monocropped midseason rice areas during 1990-91 regional trials in Hunan Province (see table). It also does well as a monocropped or dual-cropped, late-season variety. Average grain yield is 7.5 t/ha.

An additional advantage is its very good ratooning ability. The average ratoon crop had a 60-65 d growth duration and yield of 5.0 t/ha from 1989 to 1991 at the Agricultural Research Institute of Changde, Hunan Province. ■

La Plata Mochi F. A., a new rice variety from Argentina

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La Plata Mochi F. A. is the first Argentine waxy rice cultivar released from the rice program of the Faculty of Agrarian and Forestry Sciences of the National University of La Plata. It was developed to satisfy the demands of Koreans and Japanese in South America.

La Plata Mochi F. A. is 100 cm tall, resists lodging, and grows vigorously. It has a 125-d growth duration and yields about 5 t/ha. The panicle is 2.1-cm-long. Grain shattering is minimal and threshability intermediate.

The caryopsis is 5.7 cm long and 3.4 cm wide, with length-width ratio of 1.7. The waxy endosperm has 1.8% amylose content, gelatinization temperature of 6.0, alkali spreading value of 1.7, and 8.5% protein content. ■

Pant Dhan 10 replaces Pant Dhan 4 and Sarju 52 in western Uttar Pradesh, India

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Pant Dhan 10 (IR9763-11-2-2-3) was developed using the pedigree method following hybridization of IR32/Mahsuri/IR28 at IRRI, Philippines. It was evaluated as IET8616 in the All India Coordinated Trials.

It is a 92-cm semidwarf that matures in 125 d. It is suitable for transplanting in

the irrigated fields of Meerut, Agra, Moradabad, and Bareilly divisions and the tarai region of Nainital District of western UP.

Pant Dhan 10 outyielded Pant Dhan 4 by 11.2% and Sarju 52 by 8.6% in the 1988-91 Standard Varietal Trials (medium) at the Regional Agricultural Testing and Demonstration Centers at Meerut, Mathura, Bareilly, and Haldwani (Table 1).

Pant Dhan 10 showed moderately resistant reaction to bacterial blight and moderately resistant reaction to sheath blight and leaf blast across several locations. Pant Dhan 10 was field resistant to stem borer, leafroller, whorl

Performance of Xiang-zhong Xian No. 3 in 1990 and 1991 regional trials. Hunan, China.

	Xiang-zhong Xian No. 3		Shan You 63 (check)	
	1990	1991	1990	1991
Av grain yield (t/ha)	8.9	8.5	8.3	8.2
Highest grain yield (t/ha)	10.0	10.8	10.0	11.2
Growth duration (d)	128	130	138	139

Table 1. Mean performance of Pant Dhan 10 at 4 locations in western UP, India. 1988-91.

Year	Mean yield (t/ha)			% increase/decrease over	
	Pant Dhan 10	Pant Dhan 4 (check)	Sarju 52 (check)	Pant Dhan 4	Sarju 52
1988	5.3	4.1	4.8	+29.2	+10.4
1989	4.8	4.6	4.2	+4.3	+14.2
1990	3.9	4.1	3.7	-5.1	+5.4
1991	5.5	4.6	5.3	+19.5	+3.8
Mean	4.9	4.4	4.5	+11.6	+6.7